

Shifts in Materials, Themes, and Artist Representation in the Finnish National Gallery Collection (1850–2010)

The Finnish National Gallery (Kansallisgalleria) is the largest museum of fine arts in Finland. It comprises the Ateneum Art Museum, the Museum of Contemporary Art Kiasma and the Sinebrychoff Art Museum. In their own words, the gallery “develops Finnish cultural heritage and makes art accessible to the public.” They also manage the national art collection and its archives, which includes approximately 43,000 works of art, as well as archival materials and artefacts. For my final project, I wanted to use this collection and explore how it has changed over the years. I think art history is an interesting and important part of Finnish history, since art was used to help shape the Finnish national identity, especially before and during independence.

The Finnish National Gallery’s collection is available online and includes a lot of metadata, such as materials used, information on the artist and web urls to photographs of the artwork. The collection has works from both Finnish and foreign artists. The oldest artworks in the collection are from the 14th century and the collection is still expanding today. I wanted to explore how the collection has changed in terms of materials used, themes and representation of artists.

My research questions are as follows:

- How have materials changed over time in the collection?
- How have themes changed over time?
- How does representation of artists change over time?

Data cleaning and processing

The data can also be accessed through an API but it is limited to 200 results per query. The dataset is large so I opted to download the full data dump locally though the [link](#) provided on the Kansallisgalleria API page. In total the JSON formatted data had about 88,000 entries. The main technologies used for data cleaning and analysis were Python and the libraries Pandas and Matplotlib. Initial preprocessing included determining how usable the dataset was. The data was converted from JSON format to a Pandas dataframe that was then saved as a CSV file. Since I was interested in materials, themes and representation the most useful metadata fields were ‘keywords’, ‘materials’, ‘category’, and ‘people’. I also needed the field ‘year’ to date the works accurately.

The dataframe was first filtered to only include entries categorised as ‘artworks’. The total number of ‘artworks’ in the collection is approximately 75,000.

```

Categories in dataset:
category.categoryId
artwork          74137
letter           9371
photo            2012
av-material      1500
artefact         635
archive          294

```

Since the data spans many centuries, I needed to define a reasonable timeframe for the analysis. The art works were grouped by decade to find out which decades had enough art works. Most earlier decades only had one or two works total, so the output was filtered to include works after 1700's. From this I was able to see that after 1850's each decade had at least 1,000 works, some decades having more than 7,000 works. This solidified the timeframe to 1850-2010. Even though 2020's had almost 1000 works already, the decade was excluded from analysis since the decade has not ended yet and only reflects the first few years. The total number of artworks from this timeframe was 53,497. Grouping artworks by decade was chosen as a compromise between temporal precision and interpretability. Year-level analysis would have been too noisy due to uneven data coverage, while broader periods would have obscured meaningful historical change.

Having the timeframe set, I moved on to explore how usable the metadata fields I was interested in were. I noticed while manually browsing through the original JSON data that the fields "materials" and "keywords" were represented as lists that might be empty. The empty lists were still categorised as non-null, when using the Pandas function info().

Original JSON data:

```
"keywords": [
  {
    "en": "sketch book",
    "fi": "luonnoskirja",
    "sv": "skissbok"
  }
],
```

```
"materials": [
  {
    "en": "paper",
    "fi": "paperi",
    "sv": "papper"
  }
],
```

```
"keywords": [],
"materials": [],
```

Partial output of `dataframe.info()`:

```
keywords      53497 non-null object
materials     53497 non-null object
```

I cleaned these fields by adding columns "materials_clean" and "keywords_clean" that included the original data as a string (multiple values were separated with ", "). With these columns the actual number of non-null values could be computed:

```
materials_clean  14506 non-null object
keywords_clean   28899 non-null object
```

The information about the artists was inside the 'people' field in the original JSON data:

```
"people": [
  {
    "id": 63259,
    "firstName": "Elias",
    "familyName": "Muukka",
    "birthDate": "1853-06-10",
    "deathDate": "1938-10-02",
    "birthPlace": "Lemi",
    "deathPlace": "Helsinki",
    "birthYear": 1853,
    "deathYear": 1938,
    "attribution": null,
    "role": {
      "id": 98595,
      "fi": "taiteilija",
      "sv": "konstnär",
      "en": "Artist",
      "type": "role"
    }
  }
]
```

I wanted this information in a cleaner format. The artist was extracted from the original data by extracting the "Artist" dictionary and creating columns for the artist's last name as well as birth year.

```
def extract_artist(person_list):
    if not isinstance(person_list, list) or len(person_list) == 0:
        return None
    for p in person_list:
        if p.get("role", {}).get("en") == "Artist":
            return p
    return person_list[0]
```

```
def add_artist_fields(df):
    df["artist"] = df["people"].apply(extract_artist)

    df["artist_last"] = df["artist"].apply(lambda x: x.get("familyName") if isinstance(x, dict) else None)
    df["artist_birth"] = df["artist"].apply(lambda x: x.get("birthYear") if isinstance(x, dict) else None)

    return df
```

The year from which the artwork was from was represented as “yearFrom” or “dateFrom” in the original JSON data. This was simplified to a column named “year” and forced into numeric format.

```
def extract_year(df):
    df["year"] = df["yearFrom"]
    if "dateFrom" in df.columns:
        df["year"] = df["year"].fillna(df["dateFrom"].str[:4])

    df["year"] = pd.to_numeric(df["year"], errors="coerce")
    return df
```

The final dataset included the 53,497 artwork entries from the defined timeframe. The materials and keywords had a lot of missing values (14,506 and 28,899 non-null values, respectively), but they still had enough valid entries for my analysis. I used the final dataset as the input for my analysis. The output was several plots made with Matplotlib, which aimed to highlight the research questions.

Information about the final dataset:

```
Index: 53497 entries, 2 to 88489
Data columns (total 8 columns):
#   Column                Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  ---                -
0   objectId              53497 non-null  int64
1   category.categoryId  53497 non-null  object
2   year                  53497 non-null  int64
3   materials_clean      14506 non-null  object
4   keywords_clean       28899 non-null  object
5   artist_last          53496 non-null  object
6   artist_birth         52719 non-null  float64
7   decade               53497 non-null  int64
dtypes: float64(1), int64(3), object(4)
```

Results

Question: How have materials changed over time in the collection?

Total artworks: 14,506

For answering the first research question, I plotted the data from different decades in a line plot. The data was normalized by scaling each decade to the mean decade size. To find out the top 10 materials, I computed two plots to make the data more readable.

From the first chart we can see that overall paper is the most common material in the collections of artworks. Paper dominance likely reflects the large number of sketches and works-on-paper in the collection, not necessarily dominance in exhibition culture. Canvas and oil follow roughly the same progression, so they are most probably used together, validating the material parsing approach. Pencil has a really high peak in the 1940's. We can also see that watercolour works arose in the 1960's but then declined.

In the table showing top 6-10 materials, we can see that ink and gouache peaked in the 1890's. Other than that the other materials are quite stable.

Question: How have themes changed over time?

Total artworks: 28899

To answer my second research question, I plotted the data in another set of line plots. This time the normalisation was done proportionally to the total number of artworks each decade. It is important to note here however, keywords are assigned by curators and may reflect later interpretive frameworks rather than artists' original intent.

From the top 5 keywords we can see that at the beginning of the timeframe artworks depicting landscapes were over one fifth of all artworks from that decade. The proportion of landscape pieces declined quickly from 1850 to 1880. From this chart we can also see that the proportion of portraits has a peak in the 1940's. The keywords "man" and "woman" follow the progression of the "portrait" keyword. Perhaps the most interesting information gathered from this chart is the rise of abstract artworks. The first abstract works were acquired only in the 1930's but the keyword has still made it to the top 5, reaching its peak in the 1960's when it was the most popular keyword proportionally to other artworks from that decade. The rise of abstraction in the 1930s–1960s aligns with broader European modernist movements, suggesting the collection reflects international artistic developments rather than just national ones. This indicates a clear thematic shift in the collection from national-romantic and representational subjects toward modernist and abstract themes during the 20th century.

From the table showing the top 6-10 keywords we can see that 'face' started rising in the 1930s, hitting its peak in the 1940s after which it declined again. In the 1990s it started rising

again and became the sixth most proportionally common keyword. This keyword follows a similar pattern as “man”, “woman”, and "portrait". The keyword “sketch book” has also held a strong position, peaking in the early 1900's and 1960-70's. This shows that a good portion of the collection is sketches. The keyword “people” has seen an overall decline.

Question: How does representation of artists change over time?

To answer my third research question, I plotted the number of unique artists represented in the collection (53,496 works total) and the average age for the artist at the time of the work (52,719 works total). The number of unique artists was counted by last names. Counting artists by last name is an approximation, it may undercount or overcount due to shared surnames or name changes.

From the chart showing the number of unique artists from each decade we can see that the number of unique names has been rising quite steadily. Rising unique artist counts may reflect diversification of artistic careers, but also changes in acquisition policy and capacity.

From the chart showing average artist age we can see that this has changed a lot. The average age for an artist at the time of their work reached the lowest (approx. 27) in the 1870s and highest (approx. 47) in the 1980. Overall the average age has gone up. These findings suggest that the collection increasingly represents a broader range of artists over time, while also reflecting longer artistic careers and later institutional recognition.

Discussion

Overall the results show clear changes in materials, themes and representation over time. The materials diversify and there has been a thematic shift from landscapes to portraits to abstraction. Also the number of unique artists has increased and average age at time of work has risen. The output results reflect works by decade, which is determined by each artwork's release year. Some of these works might have been acquired much later to the year they are from.

Limitations and biases

The Finnish National Gallery is not a neutral sample of Finnish art production. Acquisition decisions reflect institutional priorities, funding, and cultural policy. The results reflect changes in the *collection*, not necessarily changes in Finnish art production as a whole. The materials analysis uses 14,506 artworks. Keyword analysis uses 28,899 artworks. Artist age analysis uses fields with only a small portion of null-values. These subsets may not be representative of the full collection and likely overrepresent well-documented artists and works, as metadata has been added later on. Older works are also more likely to have missing materials/keywords. Later works benefit from standardised digital cataloguing.

There are also some analytical limitations. Last names do not fully reflect unique artists, since artists may have the same last name or change names during their lifetime. Keywords also do not reflect intrinsic themes. For example, a portrait can have multiple themes, depending on the angle, subject, background or other part of the artwork. An additional limitation is survivorship bias. Artworks that have been preserved, catalogued, and acquired by a national institution are more likely to be by well-established artists or from durable media.

Interpretation of results

The decline of landscape dominance after the 19th century aligns with the waning of national-romantic visual culture. The rise of abstraction corresponds to modernism and post-war internationalisation. Increasing artist age at time of work may reflect longer artistic careers, institutional recognition later in life and/or changing career sustainability. I think rather than producing definitive claims about Finnish art history, this project shows how computational analysis of museum metadata can surface long-term patterns while simultaneously revealing the institutional and cataloguing structures that shape cultural memory.

Computation allowed me to identify long-term patterns across tens of thousands of artworks. At the same time, it required simplifying assumptions and careful normalisation. Without computational methods, identifying these long-term patterns across more than 50,000 artworks would not have been feasible. At the same time, the project demonstrates that computational analysis in the humanities must be accompanied by critical reflection on data provenance, metadata construction, and institutional context.